

GraphRAG In The Field Of General Question Answering: A Survey

Carina Obster M.A.
University of Vienna
Carina.Obster@web.de

Abstract

Graph-based Retrieval-Augmented Generation (GraphRAG) is an innovative framework that combines Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) with the structured knowledge representation of Knowledge Graphs (KGs), enabling more informed and context-aware text generation. Despite its growing potential, research in this area remains underdeveloped, with existing surveys mainly covering the integration of Large Language Models (LLMs) and KGs in general. Notably, there is a lack of a task-oriented, performance-driven analysis specific to GraphRAG methods. This paper addresses these gaps by presenting a survey specifically focused on GraphRAG methodologies, with a particular emphasis on their application to the downstream task of Question Answering (QA). By centering the analysis on this task, the survey aims to provide practical insights for researchers and practitioners working in QA contexts. It presents a detailed overview of methods, datasets and evaluation metrics, relevant to QA. Additionally, it categorizes existing studies and highlights emerging trends and challenges that are most pertinent to this domain. Through this focused and in-depth analysis, this paper seeks to provide a comprehensive overview and basis for the application of GraphRAG in QA.

1 Introduction

In the recent past, there have been many attempts to integrate KGs into LLMs, with various goals. Among the most important ones is improving knowledge recall and accuracy of LLMs, thereby reducing hallucinations (Magham, 2024). KGs can make LLMs, typically treated as black box models, explainable and interpretable (Jiang et al., 2023b). Furthermore, KGs can provide LLMs with domain-specific knowledge, allowing to fine-tune a model to a domain (Yang et al., 2024). Regarding the methodology of integrating KGs into LLMs, there

are several approaches, including pre-training and fine-tuning with KG data (Pan et al., 2023), embedding alignment (Pan et al., 2024), and prompt engineering (Pan et al., 2023). One of the most promising new trends is the integration via RAG: GraphRAG is a novel framework that combines RAG with KGs to enhance knowledge-aware text generation (Peng et al., 2024). It leverages structured knowledge in graph form, linking relevant graph data, and, additionally, documents, to input queries, enabling a model to generate informed responses by integrating both retrieved information and graph-based contextual knowledge.

This paper intends to provide an overview of the current methods of implementing GraphRAG. The motivation for this survey stems from some gaps in the existing body of research. Current surveys on the integration of LLMs and KGs predominantly focus on approaches unrelated to RAG, such as pre-training LLMs with KGs or using LLMs for KG construction (Pan et al., 2023). Furthermore, almost none of the existing surveys provide a detailed overview of methods, datasets and evaluation metrics. This scarcity of detailed reviews necessitates a focused examination of GraphRAG methodologies.

This paper aims to address these gaps by providing a comprehensive survey of GraphRAG methods, with a specific focus on their application to the downstream task of QA. It seeks to present a thorough overview of QA-related GraphRAG methods, datasets and evaluation metrics. By adopting a task-based structure that prioritizes QA, the survey emphasizes practical utility for researchers and practitioners interested in this particular task. Additionally, the paper identifies emerging trends and challenges, all within the context of their implications for QA.

QA tasks are highly representative of the challenges GraphRAG aims to address, such as precise retrieval, contextual understanding, and generation

accuracy. Besides, QA is a downstream task with clear evaluation metrics, making it easier to benchmark and compare different methods.

2 Related Work

Since GraphRAG is a relatively recent development, only surveys published within the past two years were considered for inclusion. Due to the limited number of surveys on this topic, works that are not yet peer-reviewed were also taken into account. The selected surveys either directly address GraphRAG or include a relevant section on GraphRAG, while surveys that focus solely on KGs, basic RAG, or hybrid methods were excluded.

[Pan et al. \(2023\)](#) examine the bidirectional integration of LLMs, which embeds parametric knowledge, and KGs, known for providing explicit knowledge structures. The paper presents recent developments and debates around how KGs can enhance LLMs via (pre-)training, prompt construction and retrieval augmented methods, while also detailing how LLMs can contribute to KG construction and knowledge extraction. By categorizing research into two main directions, LLMs for KGs and KGs for LLMs, the survey provides a qualitative comparison of current methodologies in a narrative form. While the survey effectively identifies gaps and suggests future research directions, it notably prioritizes the enhancement of KGs via LLMs over the reverse. Certain areas, such as domain-adapted LLM fine-tuning through KGs and KG Reasoning, remain less explored, highlighting opportunities for further investigation. Additionally, the rapid development of retrieval-augmented methods like GraphRAG suggests the need for an update on this survey.

[Peng et al. \(2024\)](#) claim to provide the first comprehensive overview of GraphRAG methodologies, aiming to define the emerging field and its core workflow components: graph indexing, graph-guided retrieval, and graph-enhanced generation. By detailing key technologies, training methods, application areas, and evaluation techniques at each stage of this pipeline, the paper offers a structured look at the GraphRAG process and suggests directions for future research. Papers are grouped based on methodologies used at each GraphRAG step, and a qualitative narrative comparison is provided that outlines key benchmarks, methods, and metrics without delving into

specific performance outcomes. Throughout the survey, discussions at the end of each workflow step highlight trends, such as hybrid approaches combining Graph Neural Networks (GNNs) with LLMs to leverage both graph and text data effectively. The analysis addresses challenges in balancing retrieval paradigms (single-pass versus iterative) and selecting appropriate graph formats and retrieval granularities (nodes, triplets, paths, etc.) to optimize accuracy, completeness, and efficiency. However, the paper does not include a quantitative comparison of these methods and lacks coverage on real-time or dynamic retrieval, leaving room for further exploration into adaptive GraphRAG strategies that could support rapidly changing data.

[Procko and Ochoa \(2024\)](#) provide a short survey mainly on GraphRAG, based on a discussion how RAG can be improved by incorporating KGs. While including a detailed description of different GraphRAG methodologies, the descriptions are simply listed, lacking an argumentative thread. Additionally, the paper lacks a systematic survey methodology section, which might limit its replicability and thoroughness in addressing all relevant research.

[Pan et al. \(2024\)](#) offer a structured overview of research efforts aimed at integrating LLMs and KGs. The paper organizes the landscape into three distinct categories: Enhancing LLMs with KGs to provide structured knowledge, applying LLMs to support KG tasks, such as embedding, completion, and construction, and exploring synergistic approaches where LLMs and KGs improve each other. By categorizing papers along these lines, the survey aims at establishing a clear taxonomy. Each paper's approach is briefly described, emphasizing contributions rather than a critical evaluation.

The survey's primary findings highlight the advantages and limitations associated with each general integration approach, with particular emphasis on the synergy of LLMs and KGs as a promising area for future research. Suggested directions include using KGs to detect hallucinations in LLM outputs and integrating multimodal LLMs with KGs. Although thorough, the survey only briefly touches upon recent developments in GraphRAG, dedicating limited discussion to this emergent method, which may warrant further attention given its relevance to KG-LLM integration.

3 Methodology

This survey paper follows the structure of the GraphRAG process, which consists of indexing, retrieval and generation (Peng et al., 2024). The detailed GraphRAG pipeline is as follows:

- **Graph Construction:** If the graph is not available yet, it needs to be constructed. Nodes and edges have to be defined, and the graph has to be stored in a format suitable for computation.
- **Query Encoding:** A user query or input is encoded into a dense vector representation using a neural network encoder, such as a transformer-based model.
- **Graph Retrieval:** The relevance of nodes or subgraphs to the query are evaluated, e.g. through similarity calculations. Relevant information, e.g. in the form of subgraphs, is retrieved.
- **Context Construction:** The retrieved information is converted into a form suitable for text generation, e.g. through linearizing the subgraph into a sequence or summarizing its content.
- **Augmented Text Generation:** The original query is combined with the context derived from the extracted KG information. The LLM generates a response based on the augmented input.

This survey will focus on the retrieval stage of the relevant methodologies.

To investigate the state of research on GraphRAG, a comprehensive literature search was conducted across the academic platforms ACL Anthology, Google Scholar, Semantic Scholar, and the German DIN page on GraphRAG.

The search was guided by the keywords ["GraphRAG"], ["Graph RAG"], ["GraphRAG QA"], ["Graph RAG QA"], ["Graph Retrieval-Augmented Generation"], and ["GRAG"], which were used to locate papers directly relevant to the integration of GraphRAG with QA tasks.

In order to ensure the selection of high-quality and pertinent research, several criteria were established:

- **Timeframe:** Given that GraphRAG is a relatively new development, only papers published within the past 2 years were considered.

- **Type of paper:** Only experimental papers were included to focus on advancements in approaches or methods related to GraphRAG.
- **Relevance:** Papers were selected based on their direct application of GraphRAG in the context of QA systems.

A total of 44 papers were initially screened for inclusion, 13 of which were included in the final result set. The rest of the papers were excluded based on predefined criteria, including papers that focus on other downstream tasks such as summarization, rather than QA. Papers that focus on multiple-choice QA or complex reasoning with multiple KG hops were excluded as well. When it comes to the choice of KGs, temporal or event KGs and general knowledge bases are not the subject of this paper. As regards methods, such requiring pre-training of models, hybrid methods or GNNs, and very advanced methods (such as using LLMs as agents to operate on KGs) are beyond the scope of this study. Papers focusing on QA in a specific domain, rather than broad applications in GraphRAG, were also disregarded.

4 Analysis

4.1 Graph-Based Indexing

As a first step in the GraphRAG pipeline, a graph database has to be constructed that aligns with the downstream task of QA, and it has to be indexed.

4.1.1 KGs and Datasets

Most of the investigated methods rely on publicly available, already established KGs such as Wikidata that accompany QA datasets, such as WebQuestions, MetaQA, Mintaka and LCQuAD (see table 1). WebQuestions is an English QA dataset containing 4,737 questions, originally built on FreeBase, including the Freebase KG. It includes questions requiring multiple hops and set intersections. tau Yih et al. (2016) have used it to construct the semantic parse dataset WebQuestionsSP, which is also used by some authors. MetaQA is a benchmark dataset introduced by Zhang et al. (2017), containing over 400,000 single- and multi-hop questions. It includes a KG (MetaQA-KG) with data about movies and a corresponding QA dataset. Other authors test their methods on datasets that require multi-hop reasoning, such as ComplexWebQuestions (Talmor and Berant, 2018). The KGs mentioned so far store general knowledge, such

as encyclopedic knowledge originating from Wiki-data and Freebase. Related to those are common-sense knowledge datasets, such as ExplaGraphs or CommonsenseQA (Talmor et al., 2019), a resource used by Li et al. (2023). Other papers utilize domain-specific datasets, such as OpenbookQA. For authors who use graph languages as a basis for LLM generation, QA datasets with queries in code are useful, such as SPCQL. Some of the investigated methods also construct their own KGs. Jin et al. (2024) construct five KGs spanning different domains (GRBench), while He et al. (2024) extract information from the dataset ExplaGraphs (Saha et al., 2021) to create their own dataset. Kim et al. (2023) utilize their previously created dataset FactKG, which allows for fact verification reasoning. While general-purpose KGs ensure rapid and broad deployment in experiments, domain-specific or custom-made KGs offer insights into how a GraphRAG method performs in a certain field of expertise. Looking at general-purpose KGs as such, common-sense KGs such as ConceptNet are better suited for scenarios requiring reasoning, whereas encyclopedic KGs provide a broader factual basis. With the GraphRAG method gaining more and more attention, one might see a trend towards tailored, domain-specific KGs.

4.1.2 Indexing

The indexing itself influences the granularity of the retrieval and the speed of query operations (Peng et al., 2024). Depending on which structure - graph, text or vector embeddings - the retrieval is performed on, different results can be expected.

The most common approach is **graph indexing**, ensuring that all nodes and edges of the graph are easily accessible through graph search algorithms, suitable for knowledge-rich queries. This method is employed by the majority of authors, as shown in table 3.

In the case of **text indexing**, graph data is first converted to text and can then be retrieved by text-based retrieval techniques (Peng et al., 2024). Li et al. (2024) and Li et al. (2023) utilize this method, thus aligning the data more closely with the format of LLMs.

Vector indexing converts graph data into vector representations, which mainly seems to benefit retrieval speed (Peng et al., 2024). Both He et al. (2024) and Hu et al. (2024) use an LM; the former to generate embeddings of the nodes and the graph, the latter to turn the text information from

the nodes and edges into embeddings, which are then averaged to create a single embedding for each subgraph.

Graph indexing is particularly effective for queries requiring intricate reasoning, since it preserves the graph's structure and facilitates graph traversal. Text indexing, on the other hand, enhances compatibility with LLMs, while possibly losing structural nuances inherent to the graph's structure. Vector indexing allows for rapid retrieval but potentially struggles with preserving fine-grained structures within the graph.

4.2 Graph-Guided Retrieval

Graph-Guided Retrieval relates to the process of extracting information from the KG in response to user queries.

4.2.1 Retriever

Non-parametric retrievers operate directly on the KG during retrieval time. He et al. (2024) utilise traditional graph search algorithm retrievers, which allegedly ensure high retrieval efficiency and transparency (Peng et al., 2024). Some papers use rule-based methods, such as semantic similarity (Baek et al., 2023), BM25 and Dense Passage Retrieval (Li et al., 2023) and pattern-matching (Li et al., 2024). Others employ query-based retrieval methods, such as cypher statements (Saleh et al., 2024).

Parametric, LM-Based retrievers rely on learned parameters. They excel in their ability to process diverse and unstructured natural language queries (Peng et al., 2024). Kim et al. (2023) use an LLM to generate the top-k relevant relations of an entity. Sen et al. (2023) use a model of the Rigel LM family. Guo et al. (2023) employ a pre-trained language model with a linear classifier to predict the hop number, which determines the maximum reasoning depth for the retrieval. Jiang et al. (2023a) use LLMs to automatically call pre-set functions that help gather and combine relevant information for better reasoning. Jin et al. (2024) put the LLM at the heart of the retrieval step: The LLM determines what information is needed and then generates specific queries to interact with the KG.

While non-parametric retrievers are a good choice for tasks that require interpretable reasoning over structured data, parametric retrievers do not offer this kind of clarity about how retrieval decisions are made, but can adapt to different queries

more easily.

4.2.2 Retrieval Paradigm

Once Retrieval aims to get all the relevant information in one retrieval step, thus being faster and more computationally efficient (Peng et al., 2024). More than half of the authors employ Once Retrieval, see table 3.

In **Iterative Retrieval**, there are multiple retrieval steps, whereby the later retrieval steps are based on the earlier steps, leading to higher computational costs and more accurate results (Peng et al., 2024). Table 3 shows that this is the less popular retrieval paradigm.

Whereas Once Retrieval prevents the system from refining its understanding of queries, Iterative Retrieval provides the system with a chance to refine the queries or add additional context with each step. Thus, the first paradigm fulfills the need for fast, efficient responses, while the second paradigm is more suited for handling queries requiring complex responses based on advanced reasoning.

4.2.3 Retrieval Granularity

The focus on **nodes** enables precise retrieval by focusing on individual elements within the graph, making it ideal for targeted queries and extracting specific information. Luo et al. (2023) retrieve entities and relations separately and then fill them in the logical forms generated by the LLM.

Triples represent entities and their relationships as subject-predicate-object triples, offering a structured way to organize relational data in a graph. This format facilitates clear and organized data retrieval, making it especially useful in scenarios where understanding relationships and contextual relevance between entities is essential. Still, it might lack some context in comparison with path or subgraph retrieval (Peng et al., 2024). Baek et al. (2023) extract relevant triples by calculating semantic similarity between queries and triples. Li et al. (2023) and Li et al. (2024) first convert each KG triplet into text and then use a text retriever to extract relevant triples. Sen et al. (2023) extract weighted triples, while Guo et al. (2023) retrieve triples from the KG, which are then combined to form a reasoning path and subgraph.

Path retrieval means that sequences of relationships between entities are retrieved. This way, more context is retrieved, and reasoning is enhanced (Peng et al., 2024). Wu et al. (2023) use an LLM to generate a "reasoning plan" and then

retrieve relevant paths based on this plan.

Compared to the other methods, **subgraph** retrieval offers the best contextual understanding and reasoning capabilities (Peng et al., 2024). Hu et al. (2024) first convert all the k-hop subgraphs from the KG into embeddings. Then, they find subgraphs related to the query by comparing how similar these embeddings are. He et al. (2024) identify relevant nodes and edges, and then construct a subgraph using the PCST algorithm. Saleh et al. (2024) extract subgraphs from the KG based on the queries.

In practice, the boundaries between these methods are blurred, as subgraphs are composed of paths, which in turn are composed of triples (Peng et al., 2024). Thus, Jiang et al. (2023a) also employ a hybrid retrieval method that ensures that the LLM adaptively selects nodes, triplet, paths or subgraphs. Jin et al. (2024) follow an entirely different path, as they do not directly extract information from the KG, but instead allow an LLM to traverse the graph node by node.

In short, node and triplet retrieval are ideal for targeted queries, whereas path and subgraph retrieval are most suitable for queries requiring contextual reasoning. Most papers focus on triplet retrieval, balancing computational cost and reasoning depth.

4.2.4 Retrieval Enhancement

Different strategies are applied to enhance user queries as well as the retrieved information (Peng et al., 2024).

Query Enhancement: Some of the investigated papers translate the query into a formal language. Li et al. (2024), for instance, translate the query into CQL code, which is then modified to align with the KG. Luo et al. (2023) convert the query into a logical form resembling a query language and then pass it on to the KG to retrieve nodes and edges.

Query Expansion extends the original query with additional relevant terms. Guo et al. (2023) analyze the query and generates variants for it.

Query Decomposition breaks down the original query into smaller sub-queries (Peng et al., 2024). Kim et al. (2023) break down the query into sub-sentences and retrieve the relevant triples for each subsentence.

These methods offer more flexibility in handling the query, which might lead to better retrieval results.

Knowledge Enhancement: Some of the investigated papers insert this extra step between KG retrieval and LLM generation to ensure that the extracted information is not only complete, but also highly relevant (Peng et al., 2024).

Guo et al. (2023) apply knowledge merging: They merge nodes and condense the retrieved sub-graph to enhance reasoning.

Knowledge pruning involves removing less relevant or redundant information from the retrieved data to improve the quality of the results (Peng et al., 2024). Li et al. (2023) use a pre-trained cross-encoder to re-rank the retrieved triplets. Kim et al. (2023) propose to use an LLM to prune irrelevant graph data. He et al. (2024) apply pruning to the retrieved subgraphs and merge them.

Retrieval Enhancement serves as a beneficial intermediary step, ensuring that either the query, the retrieved information or both are optimized for further processing.

4.3 Graph-Enhanced Generation

When integrating LLMs with graph data, the graph must first be converted into specific formats that preserve its relational and hierarchical structure. This ensures the LLMs can effectively interpret the data. After formatting, the graph data is combined with a query and processed by the LLM (Peng et al., 2024).

The retrieved graph data can be given to the LLM in the form of a graph languages, a formalized notation to represent graph data. An example of this is the adjacency table, which lists the immediate neighbors of each node, providing a compact representation of connections in sparse graphs. He et al. (2024) turn the triples in the retrieved sub-graph into a simple list, then combine them and input them into the LLMs. Luo et al. (2023) convert the retrieved information into SPARQL queries.

The most obvious and most widely used approach (see table 3) is to feed the retrieved information to the LLM in the form of natural language prompts. By translating the graph data into clear and simple language, LLMs make it easier for users to understand (Peng et al., 2024). Saleh et al. (2024) and Sen et al. (2023) feed the retrieved information to the LLM using natural language, while preserving the original triplet structure. Li et al. (2024) recommend creating a natural language template for each type of edge and then inserting the nodes into the right template based on the edge type. Wu et al. (2023) first generate an edge table

of retrieved subgraphs, then let the LLM rewrite the subgraphs in natural language. Jin et al. (2024) and Jiang et al. (2023a) integrate information of different granularity from the graph in the form of natural language.

Some papers also use graph embeddings to supply the LLM with supporting information well-suited for neural networks. Hu et al. (2024) feed graph tokens to the LLM along with text tokens.

In short, graph language prompts retain structural and relational details and are thus suitable for complex reasoning tasks, while natural language prompts ensure compatibility with LLMs, with most investigated methods using a natural language prompt which is constrained by some kind of structure. Graph embedding prompts may serve as additional information targeted towards neural models.

Generation Enhancement. Not only the query and the retrieved information, but also sometimes the generated output is subject to enhancement, which mainly involves combining multiple generated answers. Kim et al. (2023), after breaking the query down into several sub-questions, generate answers for each sub-question and finally merge the answers of all sub-questions to get the final answer. Li et al. (2024) obtain answers both from feeding the models with CQL and triplets in the form of natural language, to which a dynamic decision algorithm is then applied.

4.4 Evaluation Metrics

Some or all of the traditional metrics accuracy, precision, recall and F1 Score are employed by Li et al. (2024) and Hu et al. (2024). Li et al. (2023), Kim et al. (2023) and He et al. (2024) use accuracy only. Baek et al. (2023) use accuracy to measure whether the generated tokens from the given prompt include one of the answer entities. These metrics are essential for understanding the basic performance of a system in terms of how well the answers match the ground truth. Sen et al. (2023) use Entity Matching (EM) for determining whether an LLM’s output contains the correct answer entities in the KG. Saleh et al. (2024) use the more forgiving answer-matching rate inspired by the entity-matching rate, which evaluates to what extent the generated responses contain the correct (gold) answers.

Other papers use metrics that are more focused at the retrieval stage, such as the ranking algorithms Hit@1 and Hits@1 (see table 2). Top-K

accuracy and Mean Reciprocal Rank (MRR) are used by Baek et al. (2023) to evaluate how well the system ranks the relevant answers.

Quite in contrast to the other papers, Jin et al. (2024) focus solely on the generation stage and uses Rouge-L to measure the longest common subsequence of words between the responses and the ground truth answers.

There is a noticeable diversity in the application of these metrics across different papers. Some papers focus on traditional retrieval-focused metrics, while others apply more generation-oriented metrics. This highlights the hybrid nature of GraphRAG systems, which blend both retrieval and generation tasks. Different papers use the same metrics but apply them in slightly varied ways, such as accuracy.

5 Discussion

In this study, we aimed to explore the use of GraphRAG for enhancing QA systems by integrating graph-based retrieval techniques. Our key findings are as follows: Firstly, general-purpose KGs facilitate quick deployment and broader experimental coverage, while domain-specific KGs shine by offering deeper insights into GraphRAG’s performance within a specialized field. Common-sense KGs are more adept at handling reasoning tasks, while encyclopedic KGs deliver broader factual content. As GraphRAG methods continue to evolve, there seems to be a growing trend toward the use of tailored, domain-specific KGs for more targeted applications.

Second, regarding the various indexing methods, graph indexing, which is used by the majority of papers, proves most effective for complex queries that require detailed reasoning, as it maintains the graph’s structure and supports easier traversal. In contrast, text indexing enhances compatibility with LLMs but may lose important structural nuances. Vector indexing, while fast for retrieval, may struggle with maintaining the intricate details of graph structures.

Third, in terms of retrieval mechanisms, most methods choose non-parametric retrievers, which are particularly advantageous for tasks requiring interpretable, structured reasoning. However, parametric retrievers, while less transparent, offer flexibility and adaptability to various query types. When it comes to the retrieval process itself, the Once Retrieval paradigm is preferred for its speed

and efficiency, while Iterative Retrieval is better suited for more complex tasks, allowing for successive refinement of queries and contextual understanding. Node and triplet retrieval are optimal for precise, targeted queries, while path and subgraph retrieval excel in providing contextual reasoning. A significant amount of research has focused on triplet retrieval, which balances computational cost with the depth of reasoning. Only some papers apply strategies to enhance the user queries and the retrieved information from the KG, thereby focusing on retrieval accuracy rather than enhancing the inputs to the retrieval model and the LLM.

Fourth, in terms of generation, graph-based language prompts preserve structural and relational information, making them ideal for complex reasoning tasks, while natural language prompts enhance compatibility with LLMs. Many approaches focus on natural language prompts, while putting certain structural constraints on them. Graph embedding prompts provide additional support for neural models.

The investigated papers use diverse baselines and evaluation metrics reflects the nascent stage of the GraphRAG field, where a consistent framework for comparison is yet to be established. This would also ensure that results of different methods are comparable.

The practical implications of our findings, such as the benefits of non-parametric retrievers for dynamic and scalable systems, are directly applicable to designing and optimizing GraphRAG-based QA systems. Our analysis of retrieval granularity offers guidance on choosing the best approach depending on whether precision or contextual reasoning is prioritized. Our observation that few papers enhance user queries or retrieved KG information underscores an opportunity to further integrate LLMs with KG-based systems. Researchers interested in leveraging LLMs for query optimization, or dynamic exploration of graphs can benefit from these insights. Lastly, our work can inspire initiatives to create benchmark datasets, standard baselines, and evaluation frameworks for fair and meaningful comparisons across GraphRAG methods.

This study is subject to several limitations stemming from the criteria used to exclude papers. First, we excluded papers focusing on downstream tasks other than QA, which might have offered transferable methods. Similarly, studies addressing complex reasoning requiring multiple KG hops or temporal/event KGs were omitted, narrowing the scope

of our findings.

Additionally, we excluded papers emphasizing hybrid methods, GNNs, or domain-specific QA applications, as well as those requiring pre-training of models, limiting the breadth of methodologies analyzed. Lastly, very advanced approaches, such as using LLMs as agents to navigate KGs, were beyond the focus of this work. While these exclusions helped maintain a targeted scope, they may have left out innovative or niche techniques with potential applications in GraphRAG-based QA systems.

6 Conclusion

In this study, we explored the potential of GraphRAG to enhance QA systems by integrating graph-based retrieval techniques. Through a comprehensive literature review of 13 experimental papers published in the last two years, we identified several trends and challenges in this emerging field. Indexing was found to be critical for efficient retrieval, with most methods opting for graph-wide indexing to ensure accessibility and speed. Non-parametric retrievers were the predominant choice, offering dynamic and scalable access to external knowledge. In terms of retrieval granularity, triplet retrieval provided precision, while subgraph retrieval excelled in contextual reasoning. Despite these advancements, few methods focused on enhancing user queries or retrieved information, leaving room for improved integration between LLMs and graph-based systems. The generation stage was dominated by natural language inputs.

Our analysis also highlighted key challenges in the field. One prominent issue is balancing the amount of information retrieved; excessive information can overwhelm the LLM or exceed input length limits (Jin et al., 2024), while insufficient retrieval hampers performance. The absence of standard datasets, evaluation metrics or baselines further complicates result comparison and benchmarking, with some papers using related studies as baselines—a reflection of the field’s nascent stage.

To address these challenges and advance the field, future research should focus on creating standardized evaluation frameworks and benchmarks, which would enable fair and consistent comparisons. Refining queries and retrieved information to optimize information flow between KGs and LLMs is another promising direction. Additionally, exploring dynamic graph exploration tech-

niques and improving granularity selection based on task requirements (Jin et al., 2024; Jiang et al., 2023a) could unlock new opportunities for more effective QA systems. By overcoming these barriers, GraphRAG-based systems can realize their potential across diverse applications.

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WebQuestions	Sen et al. (2023); Wu et al. (2023)
WebQuestionsSP	Baek et al. (2023) (Hu et al., 2024; Wu et al., 2023) (Luo et al., 2023; Guo et al., 2023) (Jiang et al., 2023a)
ComplexWebQuestions	Sen et al. (2023); Luo et al. (2023)
MetaQA	Saleh et al. (2024); Kim et al. (2023) (Wu et al., 2023; Guo et al., 2023; Jiang et al., 2023a)
Mintaka	Baek et al. (2023); Sen et al. (2023)
CommonsenseQA	Li et al. (2023)
LC-QuAD	Sen et al. (2023)
OpenbookQA	Li et al. (2023)
SpCQL	Li et al. (2024)
ExplaGraphs	Hu et al. (2024)
Own Dataset	Jin et al. (2024); Kim et al. (2023)

Table 1: Datasets

Evaluation Metrics	Papers
Accuracy	He et al. (2024); Baek et al. (2023) (Li et al., 2023; Kim et al., 2023) (Luo et al., 2023)
Precision	Li et al. (2024)
Recall	Li et al. (2024); Hu et al. (2024)
F1 Score	Li et al. (2024); Hu et al. (2024); Luo et al. (2023)
Entity Overlap	Sen et al. (2023)
Answer Matching Rate	Saleh et al. (2024)
Rouge-L	Jin et al. (2024)
GPT4 Score	Jin et al. (2024)
hit@1	He et al. (2024); Hu et al. (2024); Wu et al. (2023)
hits@1	Luo et al. (2023); Guo et al. (2023); Jiang et al. (2023a)
MRR	Baek et al. (2023)
Top-K accuracy	Baek et al. (2023)

Table 2: Evaluation Metrics

Method	Description	Papers
Indexing	Graph indexing	Jin et al. (2024), Sen et al. (2023), Baek et al. (2023), Saleh et al. (2024), Kim et al. (2023), Wu et al. (2023), Luo et al. (2023), Guo et al. (2023)
	Text indexing Vector indexing	Li et al. (2024), Li et al. (2023) He et al. (2024); Hu et al. (2024)
Graph-guided retrieval	Non-parametric retrievers	He et al. (2024); Baek et al. (2023); Li et al. (2023, 2024, 2023)
	Parametric retrievers	Kim et al. (2023); Sen et al. (2023); Guo et al. (2023); Jiang et al. (2023a); Jin et al. (2024)
Retrieval paradigm	Once retrieval	Hu et al. (2024); Li et al. (2023); Kim et al. (2023); Li et al. (2024); Saleh et al. (2024); Sen et al. (2023); He et al. (2024); Baek et al. (2023); Luo et al. (2023)
	Iterative retrieval	Wu et al. (2023); Jin et al. (2024); Guo et al. (2023); Jiang et al. (2023a)
Retrieval granularity	Nodes	Luo et al. (2023)
	Triplets	Baek et al. (2023); Li et al. (2023,?, 2024); Sen et al. (2023); Guo et al. (2023)
	Path	Wu et al. (2023)
	Subgraph	Hu et al. (2024); He et al. (2024); Saleh et al. (2024)
	Hybrid	Jiang et al. (2023a)
Retrieval enhancement	Query enhancement: Query enhancement Query expansion Query decomposition	Li et al. (2024); Luo et al. (2023) Guo et al. (2023) Kim et al. (2023)
	Knowledge enhancement: Knowledge merging Knowledge pruning	Guo et al. (2023) Li et al. (2023); Kim et al. (2023); He et al. (2024)
Graph-enhanced generation	Graph language prompt	He et al. (2024); Luo et al. (2023)
	Natural language prompt	Li et al. (2023); Baek et al. (2023); Guo et al. (2023); Saleh et al. (2024); Sen et al. (2023); Li et al. (2024); Wu et al. (2023); Jin et al. (2024); Jiang et al. (2023a)
	Graph embedding prompt	Hu et al. (2024)
Generation enhancement		Kim et al. (2023); Li et al. (2024)

Table 3: Methods